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Policy Maker Research Policy

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for Policy Makers in advancing Open Science. **Policy Makers play a key role in creating the strategic conditions that promote Open Science practices and ensure their integration into national and international research frameworks.** They work with stakeholders to establish, implement, and govern policies that support the adoption of Open Science, providing the necessary frameworks, resources, and partnerships that enable the transparent, collaborative, and accessible use of research data.

In the Open Science ecosystem, Policy Makers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. **Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.**

The MVS for Policy Makers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as '**Research Policy/Decision Maker Facilitating Open Science**'. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as '**Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker**'.

POLICY MAKER - RESEARCH POLICY

Research Policy/Decision Makers act as facilitators for the development and promotion of Open Science policies. They create frameworks and provide the necessary support to promote the adoption of OS practices at national and international levels. This includes mobilizing resources, building partnerships, and ensuring policies align with OS principles like FAIR.

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Research Policy Maker, Science Policy Facilitator, Strategic Policy Advisor.

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- In-depth understanding of science practice, OS and FAIR principles and practices.
- Expertise in establishing appropriate strategies, frameworks and courses of action to foster and enhance OS.
- Ability to relate OS practices to the interests of Research Performing Organisations, Funders, and other stakeholders.
- Ability to assess the financial sustainability of policy outcomes.
- Knowledge about Intellectual property rights and non-personal data management.
- Knowledge of Ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research.
- Knowledge of legal issues related to data governance including data use agreements and personal data regulations.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation. • Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources. • Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations. • Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies. • Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources. |
|---|--|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Promotes and supports OS.
- Engages all the appropriate target audiences & key stakeholders.
- Identifies actions to advance policies on FAIR and OS at the relevant level (e.g. national, thematic).
- Understands the importance of addressing gaps in provision of digital skills for FAIR and OS.
- Promotes digital skills for data intensive science transferable across different sectors.
- Sets up policies or a strategic framework which serve to promote a preferred course of action and could include financial support research.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- Frameworks and incentives are established to enhance the implementation of Open Science, with the financial commitment to ensure its continuous support.
- Appropriate partnerships with key stakeholders are established.
- A team of Open Science experts is built up to inform policy implementation

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Perform project management](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Promote the participation of citizens in scientific and research activities](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Increase the impact of science on policy and society](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Promote the transfer of knowledge](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Solve problems](#); [Identify problems](#); [Show initiative](#); [Plan](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Comply with regulations](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Exercise rights and responsibilities](#).

ResearchComp: Strategic thinking; Systemic thinking; Mobilise resources; Promote citizen science.

Terms4FAIRskills: [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain](#); [Resource management](#); [Information security](#); [Data policy](#); [Data governance](#); [Privacy governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Advocacy](#); [Financial management](#).

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